

Research Outputs of the PhD in Electroacoustic Composition, Sonic Arts, and Intermedia Applications
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17408416

Dancing House: Deconstructivism in the language of Nicola Monopoli

Marco Mancini

PhD student in Electroacoustic Composition, Sonic Arts, and Intermedia Applications at the 'U. Giordano' Conservatory of Foggia, Italy.

Copyright © 2025 Marco Mancini. This article is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Abstract The concept of deconstruction spread throughout the twentieth century thanks to the critical thought of philosopher Jacques Derrida, who sought to respond to the need for a linguistic and semantic translation of Heidegger's call for the *Destruktion* of metaphysical concepts. Derrida's deconstructionist vision decisively influenced the artistic movements that emerged over the course of the twentieth century, giving rise - among various art forms - to architectural Deconstructivism.

In the field of music, the philosopher's perspective manifested in various approaches to dismantling the essential components of musical language; however, unlike in architecture, it did not culminate in the establishment of a fully-fledged deconstructivist current. It is within this state of the art that the creative output of composer Nicola Monopoli is situated: he consciously and faithfully adopts the principles of architectural deconstructivism, drawing inspiration from one of its most emblematic structures, Prague's Dancing House.

The composition for alto saxophone and electronics under examination—bearing the same name as the building—represents the first work by the composer from Barletta based explicitly on the principles of architectural deconstructivism.

Keywords Saxophone, Electronics, Deconstructivism, Musical composition

1. Introduction (philosophical origins and theories of deconstructionism)

Deconstructivism (or deconstruction) has its roots in the thought of Jacques Derrida. In his *Of Grammatology* (1967), Derrida critiques Western logocentrism, namely the absolute primacy accorded to “logical thought” and to the spoken word as the locus of truth. He shifts the focus to writing (understood as any written sign), considering it an operative terrain in which concepts are never fixed but are defined through a continuous play of differences and deferrals.

This implies that any text—philosophical, architectural, or artistic—possesses neither an ultimate origin nor a univocal meaning; rather, it is “an irredeemably plural reality,” composed of traces that overlap without a stable center. In this sense, deconstruction entails questioning the major conceptual oppositions (“presence/absence,” “speech/writing,” “light/dark,” etc.), exposing their internal contradictions and *aporie* (impossible transitions)

The deconstructive approach quickly spread beyond pure philosophy, being adopted as a critical method across various disciplines. In particular, American literary criticism of the 1970s (the so-called “Yale School”) applied deconstruction to textual analysis. Critics such as Paul de Man, Harold Bloom, Geoffrey Hartman, and J. Hillis Miller—while rejecting stable meaning—explored how literary works conceal internal fractures within language.

Within this framework, the text becomes an open labyrinth of interpretations, where no authentic hidden truths exist, but only infinite openings and shifts of meaning.

2. Applications in visual arts, architecture, and cultural criticism

Deconstructivism has had a profound influence on the visual arts, and contemporary architecture in particular. Since the late 1980s, architects such as Frank O. Gehry, Daniel Libeskind, Rem Koolhaas, Peter Eisenman, Zaha Hadid, and Bernard Tschumi have translated Derridean principles of fragmentation and discontinuity into concrete form.

For instance, Gehry's house in Santa Monica (1977–88) is a collage of materials (concrete, corrugated metal sheets, wire mesh) that amplifies and dismantles the traditional form of a suburban dwelling. Similarly, Libeskind's design for the Jewish Museum in Berlin (1989–98) employs dramatic ruptures and symbolic voids to "demonstrate the impossibility of historicising the tragedy of the Shoah".

Even more emblematic is the Dancing House, designed by Vlado Milunić and Frank Gehry between 1992 and 1996, an authentic example of architectural deconstructivism, described by its authors as a kind of "new Baroque".

In this case, architecture itself becomes a sort of "deconstructed text" without a single point of view: fractured walls, misaligned force lines, and labyrinthine spaces overturn the traditional figure-ground hierarchy.

Figure 1. Dancing House in Praga.

Figurative literature and the visual arts have likewise embraced deconstructive practices. Postmodern artists often superimpose styles and images in irreverent contexts (consider collage or conceptual painting), challenging traditional oppositions between form and content.

Similarly, cultural criticism employs deconstruction to analyse mass media, fashion, and contemporary society. For example, communication theorists and media scholars often apply Derrida's notion of "*différance*" to reveal contradictions embedded in political discourse or cultural symbols.

A specialised essay by philosopher Pietro Terzi even speaks of a veritable "disciplinary atlas of deconstruction": in addition to literary and architectural criticism, it

encompasses media, pop culture, and even fashion, demonstrating how deconstruction has become a fashionable method across multiple domains.

In summary, deconstructive aesthetics is not confined to architecture; it permeates contemporary artistic and cultural reflection, continually inviting us to question certainties and dominant narratives.

3. Deconstructivism in music: from classical music to contemporary genres

Music, too, has seen figures inclined toward the deconstruction of the foundational elements of existing languages.

Historically, twentieth-century composers applied principles analogous to those of Derrida. In John Cage (1912–1992), one clearly finds an approach that challenges the traditional rules of composition. Cage famously declared: "As long as we live, there will be sounds," meaning that absolute silence is impossible to experience (a parallel to the impossibility of the "self" experiencing its own death). In his renowned *4'33"*, Cage "decontextualises" sound by allowing the environment and accidental noises to become an integral part of the musical work. More broadly, his practice of the prepared piano and the use of everyday sound objects expand the sonic "palette" to include every existing sound.

4. Basic principle of Dancing House

Nicola Monopoli, an Italian composer and electroacoustic performer, grounds his artistic vision in a natural and instinctive approach to the compositional act itself. To this compositional imprint, he pairs a structured mathematical and computational knowledge, enabling him to preserve all orders of beauty derived from an understanding of the concept of musical form.

In 2024, the idea emerged to begin composing electroacoustic works inspired by the concept of deconstructivism applied to music. Specifically, architectural deconstructivism proved to be the most suitable framework for contextualizing certain principles, allowing for new ways of representing foundational musical elements such as timbre, frequency, time, and rhythm through the use of electronics and acoustic instruments.

The first work in this context is *Dancing House*, for alto saxophone and electronics, inspired by the eponymous building in Prague. The electroacoustic techniques employed involve percussion samples processed through slowing down and speeding up, in order to curve the perceived rhythmic profile and consequently alter its perceptual category: the playback speed of the sample is

modified while the pitch remains unchanged (*time-stretching*).

Takes were recorded with the alto saxophone to be integrated into the electronic part; these samples are used both in their original form and processed with various techniques in the domains of frequency, time, and amplitude, including equalization, reverberation, and sound degradation effects such as *bit-crushing*.

The compositional technique applied to the management of events is based on a layering of samples, used both in their original state and in processed form. Perceptually, this creates an acoustic decontextualization relative to the source material, which in turn produces a deconstruction of the original sounds.

5. Spectral moments

The aim of the present research is to analyze the work *Dancing House* through the use of spectral moments, a specific signal analysis technique.

The term spectral moments refers to estimates of measurement characteristics, known as spectral descriptors, obtained through a statistical analysis of data. Specifically, it refers to the moments of the spectral distribution—mathematical functions used to characterize a signal with respect to its frequency representation. In this study, rather than extracting information from groups of values corresponding to measurements of physical quantities, the descriptors are used to derive information from the frequency spectrum of a sound.

Different types of spectral moments are defined to describe various aspects of the spectrum:

- Type 1:
Spectral Centroid: represents the center of gravity of the energy in the frequency domain; it is the value around which the signal's energy is, on average, concentrated.
- Type 2:
Spectral Bandwidth: measures how the energy spreads around the centroid. A large bandwidth indicates that the sound is distributed across a wide range of frequencies (e.g., noise), whereas a small bandwidth indicates concentration on a few frequencies (e.g., a pure tone).
- Type 3:
Spectral Skewness: indicates whether the energy content is more biased toward high or low frequencies. A positive value signifies a predominance of high-frequency components, while a negative value indicates a predominance of low-frequency components.

- Type 4:
Spectral Kurtosis: describes how peaked or flat the spectrum is. A high kurtosis indicates that much of the energy is concentrated in a few distinct peaks, whereas a low kurtosis signifies a flatter and more uniform spectral distribution.

In addition to the aforementioned moments, spectral Rolloff and Spectral Flatness will also be considered. Although they are not true moments in the strict statistical sense, they provide important details and a broader perspective in the analysis of sound spectra:

- **Spectral Rolloff** is defined as the frequency below which a certain percentage of the total signal energy is contained; typically, 85% or 95% of the energy is used. Given a chosen threshold (e.g., 85%), the rolloff frequency f_{rolloff} is the frequency below which 85% of the spectral energy lies. This measure provides an immediate indication of how far a sound extends before its energy becomes negligible and is useful for distinguishing sounds with strong attacks, which contain substantial energy in the high-frequency range.
- **Spectral Flatness** is defined as the ratio between the geometric mean and the arithmetic mean of the spectrum.

Values close to 1 → flat spectrum, similar to white noise (energy distributed uniformly);

Values close to 0 → highly “structured” spectrum, dominated by a few frequencies (pure tone or harmonic sound)

The following table provides a general overview of the information that can be extracted from the analysis of spectral moments, offering a clearer perspective on how the concept of musical deconstructivism is realized and expressed.

Moment	Measures	Used for
Centroid	The value around which the signal's energy is, on average, concentrated	Brightness, timbral sharpness
Bandwidth	Indicates how the energy spreads around the centroid	The width of a central frequency; a large bandwidth implies that the sound is spread across a wide range of frequencies (e.g., noise), whereas a small bandwidth indicates concentration on a few frequencies (e.g., pure tone).
Rolloff	The frequency limit of the spectral content	Gives an immediate idea of how far a sound extends before its energy becomes negligible; useful for distinguishing sounds with strong attacks, which contain significant energy in high frequencies.
Flatness	The ratio between the geometric mean and the arithmetic mean of the spectrum.	Noisiness versus pure tone
Skewness	Indicates whether the energy content is more biased towards high or low frequencies.	<p>Skewness > 0 (low-frequency bias): energy is concentrated in low frequencies, with a long tail towards the high frequencies. → Example: a soft sound with a bright attack.</p> <p>Skewness < 0 (high-frequency bias): energy is concentrated in high frequencies, with a tail towards the low frequencies. → Example: a bright sound with body in the lows (rare, can occur with effects or reverb).</p> <p>Skewness ≈ 0: the spectrum is symmetric and balanced.</p>
Kurtosis	Describes the concentration of the spectrum	Indicates how "peaked" or "flat" the spectral distribution is

Table 1

6. Analysis of Dancing House: intro

The work begins with an introduction in which the main theme is presented by the electronics, while the alto saxophone sustains an A pedal tone (concert pitch), whose frequency is subtly bent—that is, slightly modified—through a change in fingering by the performer. This pedal embodies the essence of the deconstructivist concept: a sound that serves as a structural pillar for the electronic material, yet, while remaining in a state of stability and balance, subtly alters its emitted frequency. One might consider employing vibrato; however, the acoustic nature of the instrument does not allow for sufficient upward frequency modulation through this technique, making the use of alternative fingerings essential.

Figure 2. A pedal (actual tone) on the alto saxophone with ascending and descending quarter-tone flexion.

Added to this requirement is a significant change in various spectral parameters resulting from the use of alternative fingerings

Figure 3. The spectral moments of A (actual tone) resulting from the basic fingering applied to the alto saxophone.

Figure 3 shows the spectral moments of A (actual tone) resulting from the basic fingering.

The numerical values of the moments are as follows:

1. Centroid: 826.8678 Hz
2. Bandwidth: 1263.7768 Hz
3. Rolloff: 946.2646 Hz
4. Flatness: 0.0000
5. Skewness: 21.5981
6. Kurtosis: 555.0222

Figure 4. Sound of the descending A (actual tone) on the alto saxophone with alternative fingering to lower the frequency.

Figure 4 shows the spectral moments of the descending A (actual tone) resulting from the alternative fingering.

The numerical values of the moments are as follows:

1. Centroid: 931.2383 Hz
2. Bandwidth: 1713.9355 Hz
3. Rolloff: 1130.1718 Hz
4. Flatness: 0.0000 Hz
5. Skewness: 27.5836
6. Kurtosis: 826.0201

Figure 5. Sound of the rising A (actual tone) on the alto saxophone with alternative fingering to lower the frequency.

Figure 5 shows the spectral moments of the rising A.

The numerical values of the moments are as follows:

1. Centroid: 683.9218
2. Bandwidth: 1099.3149
3. Rolloff: 718.2719
4. Flatness: 0.0000
5. Skewness: 29.7389
6. Kurtosis: 921.1731

For the quantitative analysis of audio samples, a Python script was developed to automate the extraction of the spectral descriptors described above. The application is built upon the Librosa and NumPy libraries and features a graphical user interface implemented in Tkinter, which allows the selection and analysis of audio files in common formats (.wav, .mp3) and the immediate initiation of the processing workflow.

The adopted procedure first involves loading the audio signal at its original sampling rate, avoiding any form of resampling that could alter the spectral content. Subsequently, the various spectral moments are computed.

The results are presented both in tabular form, displaying numerical values for each parameter, and as bar charts generated using the Matplotlib library, thereby facilitating comparisons between different samples. The implementation also includes an error-handling system to ensure robustness in the case of invalid files or unsupported formats.

This approach enables an objective and reproducible characterization of the audio samples, simplifying both the systematic comparison of different signals and the integration of the data into subsequent statistical analyses.

Figure 6. Comparison of spectral moments between descending A (actual tone) and ascending A (a. t.) played with different fingerings.

From Figure 6, it can be observed how the same sound, when played with different fingerings, exhibits substantial differences, highlighted not only perceptually but also through the spectral descriptors used to extract its characteristics. The direction of these changes is less relevant than the fact that the modification occurs, which is why the composer does not specify a particular fingering to be used. Priority is given to the bending of the sound, considered holistically rather than solely from the perspective of its pitch.

In the case of the samples analyzed, extracted from a studio recording, the sound significantly alters its perceptual character across three descriptors: Centroid, Bandwidth, and Rolloff.

These data provide a clear indication of how the sound is modified: the energy centroid in the frequency domain

decreases markedly when a fingering that raises the pitch is used; specifically, the Centroid shifts from 931.2383 Hz for the descending A to 683.9218 Hz for the ascending A. This indicates that the sound becomes darker and less bright, despite the increase in pitch through the second fingering.

The Rolloff value also decreases, highlighting a loss of energy and harmonic richness.

A particularly noteworthy finding concerns the spectral Bandwidth, which nearly halves when moving from the descending-A fingering to the ascending-A fingering; under this parameter, the sound changes its nature, losing much of the noisy component present with the first fingering in favor of a purer and clearer tone.

In this initial section, the electronics present two main elements developed on this bent foundation of the acoustic instrument: one rhythmic and one melodic. Both are already articulated according to the initial idea of deconstruction, albeit in a nascent form. The melodic line consists of pre-recorded phrases of the alto saxophone, including both standard tones and multiphonics; in the latter case, the highest note of the multiphonic is emphasized to make the melody recognizable, even if timbrally distorted by the extended technique. The rhythmic component, in contrast, is bent through modifications of the rhythmic profile, with continuous and irregular changes in sample playback speed, without altering pitch, and accompanied by timbral variations.

6.1. Central section analysis

The alto saxophone introduces, through sequences of impulses—first as repeated notes and subsequently as *slaps*—the material assigned to the electronics: fragments of pre-recorded saxophone melodies and rhythms that have been reworked and processed, accompanied by percussive samples. The acoustic instrument integrates into this bent soundscape, echoing the rhythmic profile of the electronic percussion through the *slap* technique.

In this dialogue between acoustic and electronic elements, an environment emerges in which a clearly defined structural framework is perceptible, interspersed with moments in which rhythm and melodies temporarily lose their equilibrium, creating a perception of structural bending. These curvatures of the rhythmic and melodic profile are reinforced by:

- the layering of elements in the electronics, which decontextualizes the original form of the pre-recorded material, later performed also by the acoustic instrument,
- the use of extended techniques that alter the spectral parameters of the emitted sound.

The use of harmonics represents a widely employed technique to characterize a deconstructed environment, even in terms of the saxophone’s sound production.

Figure 7. Use of harmonics, slaps, and multiphonics.

Among the various harmonics employed, those of D (concert pitch) and A (concert pitch) are considered, as they are most prominently featured throughout the work.

Figure 8. Comparison of spectral moments between the D3 played staccato (concert pitch) and the harmonic of the D3 played staccato (concert pitch).

Figure 9. Comparison of spectral moments between the A3 played staccato (concert pitch) and the harmonic of the A3 played staccato (concert pitch).

From the comparison of the spectral moments of the D and A notes performed using different techniques, a very interesting observation emerges: in both cases, the moments related to the Centroid, Spectral Bandwidth, and Rolloff are significantly lower in the note produced via the harmonic of the lower fundamental D.

The comparative values are as follows:

	D	D as harmonic
Centroid	2077.6878 Hz	1557.3869
Bandwidth	3020.1623	2245.2538
Rolloff	4128.2227	2686.6812
Flatness	0.0029	0.0010
Skewness	12.1431	7.3802
Kurtosis	159.5551	65.7345

	A	A as harmonic
Centroid	3023.1059	1929.1882
Bandwidth	3478.5527	2344.0662
Rolloff	6004.1748	3160.8814
Flatness	0.0100	0.0005
Skewness	5.3868	8.0827
Kurtosis	38.4870	70.5520

The data highlight how the production of the same sound using different techniques, associated with different fingerings, induces a significant variation in the spectral moments, despite producing only minor perceptual differences in the resulting sound. This observation reflects the deconstructivist concept within the sonic domain.

In architecture, observing deconstructivist works allows one to experience an unconventional sense of balance, a relationship between asymmetries inherent in modern culture and classical environmental contexts, all in symbiosis with a perceptual experience that does not detach the artistic product from the environment in which it manifests. Translating these observations into the musical domain enabled the creation of a sound context in which the bending of the constituent elements of sound does not estrange them from the musical environment, which comes to life through the symbiosis of electronic and acoustic worlds.

As the composition unfolds, the electronics reintroduce the material proposed by the saxophone, applying sound degradation processes, reverberation, and layering of the overall material. The rhythm performed by the saxophone mirrors the irregular rhythm of the electronics, emphasized

through the *slap* technique; the two rhythms intertwine, enhancing the perception of instability. The *slapped* notes are interwoven with sounds produced in their various forms—standard tones or harmonics—creating a sonic environment that *bends* its own nature.

Figure 10. D2 (actual pitch) sound of the alto saxophone using the slap technique.

Multiphonics also play an essential role in the direction of deconstruction. It is important to highlight the two approaches to this extended technique, as each offers a different contribution to the foundational concept of *Dancing House*.

In the more widespread school of thought, multiphonics are treated as timbral expressions of the instrument, with priority given to the overall perceived sound; in this approach, no specific note within the multiphonic is assigned greater thematic weight. During the airstream, the goal is to produce the sounds contained within the effect as evenly and naturally as possible.

In the second school of thought, primarily promoted by the French saxophonist and pedagogue Jean-Marie Londeix, the priority is to emphasize a single note whose prominence is greater than the other sounds within the multiphonic. Typically, this note is the highest pitch of the multiphonic, allowing the lower sounds, including the fundamental, to be preserved.

This method of performing multiphonics enables the work to explore an additional pathway for bending the frequency of the same fundamental.

Two significant examples are the use of the A2-B♭3 multiphonic (concert pitches) and the two similar versions with the thematic note emphasized on the high E4 (concert pitch); these multiphonics, combined with others present in the score, reconstruct the melodic line introduced by the electronics in the introduction in a deconstructed and timbrally distorted manner, approaching the colors generated by the electronic dimension.

Figure 11. Two similar versions of multiphonics with the thematic note emphasized on the high E4 (concert pitch).

The central section of *Dancing House* thus develops according to this conceptual line, creating continuous dialogues between the two sonic dimensions, merging, blending, and intertwining them into a distorted whole. At times, the saxophone acts as a disruptor of the created landscape, influencing the behavior of the electronics; at other times, it is the electronics that generate inertia, increasing the sonic weight before rapidly dissipating it.

6.2. Coda analysis

Dancing House concludes by returning to its point of departure: a distant echo of the initial theme presented by the electronics, sustained by white noise, while the saxophone generates rhythmic and percussive combinations on the A fundamental (concert pitch), the same as at the beginning, accompanied by slapped notes, multiphonics, and frequency bends of the fundamental achieved through alternating fingerings.

The percussive element is thus entrusted to the saxophone in the closing, while the sonic environment gradually dissolves into white noise

Figure 12. Rhythms of the A2 fundamental (concert pitch) with alternating fingerings to produce slight frequency oscillations, combined with slapped attacks and multiphonics.

7. Conclusions

The research presented here has highlighted how the principles of deconstructivism, originating in philosophy and later translated into visual arts and architecture, can also find a fertile application in contemporary musical language. The analysis of Nicola Monopoli's *Dancing House* demonstrates how the decomposition and bending of sonic parameters—frequency, timbre, rhythm, and time—generate a perceptual experience akin to that in architecture, where equilibrium and instability coexist in dynamic tension.

The direct collaboration between composer and performer is fundamental to the creation of a musical work that is truly alive and fully self-aware. The composer contributes vision, structure, and artistic intention, while the performer brings practical experience, sonic sensitivity, and a deep understanding of the instrument. Through dialogue, the two refine every detail — from expressive nuance to technical gesture — ensuring that the music is not only well written, but also effective in its sonic realization. Within this exchange, the work attains coherence, depth, and authenticity, emerging as a shared product of creative intellect and interpretative sensitivity.

The use of *spectral moments* as an analytical tool has made it possible to objectivize the compositional processes carried out, showing that deconstructivist practice is not merely an aesthetic intuition, but a method verifiable on both technical and scientific grounds. This research aims to contribute to the connection between philosophical theories, architectural principles, and compositional practices, opening new perspectives on the relationship between form and sonic perception.

Future developments may focus on applying these same principles to broader performative contexts, investigating the interplay between architectural space, live electronics, and multimedia interaction, thereby further expanding the boundaries of research on musical deconstructivism.

Acknowledgements

This paper is part of the research outputs of the PhD in Electroacoustic Composition, Sonic Arts, and Intermedia Applications (XL Cycle) at the Conservatorio di Musica “Umberto Giordano” in Foggia. The research was funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU and the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR), within the framework of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) under the initiative *Italia Domani*.

REFERENCES

- Derrida, J. (1967). *De la grammatologie*. Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit.
- Heidegger, M. (1927). *Sein und Zeit*. Tübingen: Max Niemeyer Verlag.
- Gehry, F.O. (1985). *Gehry Talks: Architecture + Process*. New York: Rizzoli.
- Eisenman, P. (1999). *Diagram Diaries*. London: Thames & Hudson.
- Libeskind, D. (2004). *Breaking Ground: Adventures in Life and Architecture*. New York: Riverhead Books.
- Hadid, Z. (2006). *Zaha Hadid: Complete Works*. London: Thames & Hudson.
- Cage, J. (1961). *Silence: Lectures and Writings*. Middletown, CT: Wesleyan University Press.
- Schaeffer, P. (1966). *Traité des objets musicaux*. Paris: Éditions du Seuil.
- Boulez, P. (1987). *Orientations: Collected Writings*. London: Faber and Faber.
- Taruskin, R. (2005). *The Oxford History of Western Music, Volume 5: The Late Twentieth Century*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kientzy, D. (1982). *Les sons multiples aux saxophones*. Paris: Salabert.
- Kientzy, D. (1991–2002). *Saxologie*. Paris: Nova Musica.
- Menzella, G. (2010). *Il sax contemporaneo*. Monza: Casa Musicale Eco.
- Rousseau, E. (1978). *Saxophone High Tones*. St. Louis: Lauren Keiser Music Publishing.
- David, V. (2023). *La technique du son au saxophone*. Paris: Billaudot.
- Londeix, J-M. (2005). *Hello! Mr. Sax ou Paramètres du saxophone*. Paris: Alphonse Leduc.
- Marzi, M. (2009). *Il saxofono*. Varese: Zecchini.
- Zermani, A. (2003). *Sax. Lo strumento del mito*. Milano: Mondadori.
- Stone, K. (1980). *Music Notation in the Twentieth Century*. New York: W. W. Norton & Co.
- Read, G. (1979). *Music Notation*. New York: Taplinger Publishing Co.
- Gould, E. (2011). *Behind Bars: The Definitive Guide to Music Notation*. London: Faber & Faber.
- Donatoni, F. (1970). *Questo*. Milano: Adelphi.